

Name	Link	Type (see the Notes tab)	CoreTrustSeal	Offer long-term preservation?	Notes
CLARIN-DK-UCPH Repository	https://rep	Diciplinary repository	Yes	Not known	The CLARIN Centre at the University of Copenhagen, Denmark, hosts and manages a data repository (CLARIN-DK-UCPH Repository), which is part of a research infrastructure for humanities and social sciences financed by the University of Copenhagen. The CLARIN-DK-UCPH Repository provides easy and sustainable access for scholars in the humanities and social sciences to digital language data (in written, spoken, video or multimodal form) and provides advanced tools for discovering, exploring, exploiting, annotating, and analyzing data. CLARIN-DK also shares knowledge on Danish language technology and resources and is the Danish node in the European Research Infrastructure Consortium, CLARIN ERIC.
DeiC Dataverse	https://dat	Institutional repository	No	Yes	DeiC Dataverse provides access to and publishing of research datasets from Danish universities. DeiC Dataverse offers preservation of data for at least 10 years.
DTU Data	https://dat	Institutional repository	Yes	Yes	Institutional data repository built on the Figshare platform. Contains research data from the Technical University of Denmark. Preservation obligations by DTU are well described - see https://www.bibliotek.dtu.dk/-/media/Andre_Universitetsenheder/Bibliotek/pdf/Guide-to-preservation-in-DTU-Data.pdf
GEUS Dataverse	https://dat	Institutional repository	No	Not known	An open data repository for scientists from the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS) to share and preserve their research data.
International Service of Geomagnetic Ind	https://isgi	Diciplinary repository	No	Not known	The International Service of Geomagnetic Indices (ISGI) is in charge of the elaboration and dissemination of geomagnetic indices, and of tables of remarkable magnetic events, based on the report of magnetic observatories distributed all over the planet, with the help of ISGI Collaborating Institutes. The interaction between the solar wind, including plasma and interplanetary magnetic field, and the Earth's magnetosphere results in a transfer of energy and particles inside the magnetosphere. Solar wind characteristics are highly variable, and they have actually a direct influence on the shape and size of the magnetosphere, on the amount of transferred energy, and on the way this energy is dissipated. It is clear that the great diversity of sources of magnetic variations give rise to a great complexity in ground magnetic signatures. Geomagnetic indices aim at describing the geomagnetic activity or some of its components. Each geomagnetic index is related to different phenomena occurring in the magnetosphere, ionosphere and deep in the Earth in its own unique way. The location of a measurement, the timing of the measurement and the way the index is calculated all affect the type of phenomenon the index relates to. The IAGA endorsed geomagnetic indices and lists of remarkable geomagnetic events constitute unique temporal and spatial coverage data series homogeneous since middle of 19th century.
MiBiG Repository	https://mit	Diciplinary repository	No	No	The MiBiG (Minimum Information about a Biosynthetic Gene Cluster) Repository stores Biosynthetic Gene Clusters (BGC) that are manually curated through community efforts. It is a central reference database for BGCs of known function, and provides the basis for comparative analyses for a number of tools. It has enabled many computational analyses of BGC function and novelty central to both small and large-scale studies of microbes and microbial communities.
Open Data DK	https://ww	Other	No	Not known	Open Data DK has established a governance model to ensure that the members perceive the association as open, equal and result-creating. Open Data DK is a union with a board and teams. The Board is the general and strategic forum and consists of a chairman and five board members. The General Assembly is the Association's decision-making body and highest authority. The individual teams coordinate efforts within specific focus areas. Governance model with teams must support the need to coordinate the work as well as possible while taking into account the autonomy that the individual teams have in terms of the democratic basic element on which the association is based. The gain of using this form of organization is a joint work across the members of the association.
Rigsarkivet ScienceRepository	https://ww https://sci	Other General repository	No No	Yes Not known	The National Archives makes Denmark's largest collection of questionnaire-based research data available to researchers and students. Order quantitative research data, conduct analyzes online and access register data and international survey data. Formerly known as the Danish Data Archive (DDA), it was the national social science data archive. Multidisciplinary research data repository, hosted by DTU, the Danish Technical University.
West African Vegetation	http://www	Diciplinary repository	No	Not known	This is a database for vegetation data from West Africa, i.e. phytosociological and dendrometric relevés as well as floristic inventories. The West African Vegetation Database has been developed in the framework of the projects "SUN - Sustainable Use of Natural Vegetation in West Africa" and "Biodiversity Transect Analysis in Africa" (BIOTA, https://www.biota-africa.org/).